

Academic Services in Islamic Education Management Study Program: The actualization of the Basic Values of the State Civil Apparatus at IAIN Palopo

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Article Information

Received: 28, July, 2020
Revised: 14, August, 2020
Online: 03, September, 2020

Keywords

State Civil Apparatus (ASN), academic services, web design, Islamic Education Management Study Program

ABSTRACT

This research aims to develop the MPI study program 's academic information to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of education services by web-based information systems by updating the State Civil Establishment (ASN) values, using the approach of Participatory Action Research (PAR). The solution to the issue of web-based academic services in IAIN Palopo 's Islamic Education Management Study Programme, namely 1) conducting consultations related to web design of the Islamic Education Management Study Programme; 2) registering the web sub - domain and collecting materials that will be the content of the Islamic Education Management Study Program web.; 3) Installing web-based machines in registered sub-domains and creating a web-based framework for the Islamic Education Management Study Program; 4) designing a web-based display of the Islamic Education Management Study Program; 5) making menus and filling each menu with types of services, information, and activities related to the Islamic Education Management Study Program; 6) Implementation of web management training for prospective web administrators of Islamic Education Management Study Program; 7) Automation of web services published in the Islamic Education Management Study Program.

INTRODUCTION

The State Civil Apparatus (ASN) is one of the most important aspects of realizing it. The State Civil Apparatus (ASN), as a state apparatus, plays a vital role in this vision. Law No. 5, 2014, on State Civil Apparatus (Indonesia, 2014) states form integrity, honesty, enthusiasm, nationalist spirit, superior, professional, neutral (free of political intervention), anti-corruption civil service. State Civil Apparatus to perform its functions properly, i.e., to implement state policy, as a public service to the community, and as an element, the glue of national unity. (Meyrina, 2017) The State Civil Apparatus has a vital role in developing the country. Sugiastuti explained that Indonesia needed a professional ASN figure, namely ASN, that was able to meet the competency standards of its position, to be able to carry out their office duties effectively and efficiently. Therefore, it is necessary to improve the performance of ASN to be more optimal and oriented to the welfare of society. (Sugiastuti, 2020)

State Islamic Institute of Palopo (IAIN Palopo), an educational college under the Ministry of Faith (Sejarah IAIN Palopo – IAIN Palopo, n.d.). Regarding the National Education System under Law No. 20 of the Year 2003, which states that national education functions to develop the capacity and shape the character and civilization of a dignified nation in the context of educating the country 's life, to develop

the potential of students to become human beings who believe in and fear God Almighty. Referring to Law No. 12 of the Year 2012 (Sopandi & Sa'ud, 2016) on higher education emphasized that higher education is based on scientific fact, logic, honesty, justice, benefits, values, obligations, plurality and affordability.

To realize these functions and goals, IAIN Palopo seeks to achieve superior, independent, and cultured human resources. The Management Education Study Program (MPI) Education and Teacher Training Faculty ("Sejarah," 2020) aimed at educating students to manage Islamic education effectively and efficiently. Educational activities and processes can be planned, organized, directed, monitored, and evaluated. Automatically, efforts to achieve Islamic education goals can be more easily realized. Moreover, the effectiveness and efficiency of Islamic education goals can be realized, not a mere utopia. (Ilham, 2020b) Problems in Islamic education (Ilham, 2020a) one of them often occurs in MPI study programs related to information systems that usually take a long time, and the lack of accurate data or data is lost. Therefore, it is a demand for MPI study program to improve the quality of the school, one of which is to develop its academic information system, because with an excellent educational information system, data processing, and student service can also increase to become a high selling power for MPI study program. The processes required in the academic information system include registration information, student re-registration, grade processing, financial data processing, course scheduling, and academic reporting. Academic information systems implemented in MPI study programs still use traditional information systems, so many weaknesses remain, such as academic data that are not well integrated, so redundancy remains. Most academic data is still stored in the form of archives, so the process of finding data is still running slowly, so data processing errors often occur, and reporting processes are still slow.

Indeed, educational service activities in the MPI Study Program can not be separated from academic, administrative services targeting lecturers and students. By looking at the number of lecturers and students in the annual MPI Study Program (PDDikti - Pangkalan Data Pendidikan Tinggi, n.d.), of course, administrative services are slower due to the number of users and the increase in service access. The service, however, remains a manual system with one operator or staff. It is the background of authors researching work units to improve web-based academic services (Indrayani, 2011) in the Management Education Study Program. In the MPI study program, however, efforts have been made to move these services even with limited access. One limitation is that the website is built using free and not premium applications, so users must tolerate the limitations. Of course, with the weaknesses of the current academic information system, the possibility of students or student parents not satisfied with academic services in the MPI Study Program. Building new academic information and service system will hopefully enable the service to be performed effectively and efficiently.

Academic Service Concept

One way to attract students is by providing services that can satisfy students. Services aimed at obtaining student satisfaction are not easy to do, often with problems in service management and unsuccessful customer satisfaction (Sri Wahyu Andayani, 2015). As Ratminto said, public service performance measurement includes: 1) Tangibles or physical appearance; 2) Reliability is the ability to deliver the promised service accurately; 3) Responsiveness or responsiveness is a willingness to help customers and conduct services sincerely; 4) Assurance or certainty is the knowledge and courtesy of workers; 5) Empathy is the treatment or personal attention given (Sri Wahyu Andayani, 2015).

Students must be treated as an asset to enhance performance. To evaluate service presentation and staff resources, educational institutions or universities are essential. Service quality can be tested by evaluating student satisfaction as students become clients. This process can be accomplished by comparing the expected quality, presented quality, and perceived quality. Information includes data entry (input) processed through a data processing model. Information results will be captured again as input, forming an information cycle that can be obtained from the information system as an organization-specific information processing system. The information system can be interpreted as a combination of people, facilities, or technological devices, media, procedures, and control over certain activities that produce the wearer's use of information. According to Indrayani, information systems can be defined as a collection of interconnected elements for integrating, processing, storing, and distributing information. (Indrayani, 2011) Web-based learning resources are certainly a difficulty in

managing change. In his writings, Johan stated that by building a management-based system, there were at least three main advantages: 1) Assist the smoothness, accuracy, and efficiency of the working mechanism of academic data processing so that information can be obtained quickly; 2) By using an academic information system online services for students who used to be slow because the data must be obtained manually, now it is faster, accurate, and relevant; and 3) Web management can improve system performance in completing tasks in the academic data reporting section (Sumarlin, 2015).

METHODS

This research is study - based scientific development research. The method used will be the Participatory Action Research (PAR) method. The PAR method is a research method focused on three forms: participation, action, and research. (Baderiah & Ilham, 2019) (Katoppo & Sudradjat, 2015)

Figure 1. Participatory Action Research (PAR) for Sustainable Community Development (*Participatory Action Research (PAR) for Sustainable Community Development – Post Growth Institute, n.d.*)

Citing Yoland Warkworth, Agus Afandi states that PAR is a term that contains a set of assumptions that underlie new scientific paradigms in seeing, studying, and changing social processes to reach conclusions about "what happened" and "what are the implications of change"(Agus Afandi, 2014). In this study, there are several steps that researchers will do as follows:

Initial Mapping

In the initial mapping phase (Rahmat & Mirnawati, 2020), researchers will go directly to the field to see how academic services form and process are performed in the MPI Study Program. Academic services to be observed consist of two forms, academic services in the study program room and web-based academic services. It is essential to see the effectiveness of both service forms.

Establish Interactions

Stages of establishing interaction (Van Schie et al., 2011) are carried out to familiarize themselves more closely with the executors of academic, administrative activities in the MPI study program. One of the ways undertaken by researchers is to help organize academic content or articles in MPI study programs.

Determination of Research Agenda

According to Yaumi, the research agenda was determined in the MPI study program together with the activity executor (M.A, 2016); this is because the researcher was alone and needed help in this research activity. Organizers will play an active role in this activity, primarily because they have worked directly in MPI study programs organizing academics so far.

Participatory Mapping

This participatory mapping stage (Iqbal et al., 2016) was conducted with the executor of academic administration activities in the MPI study program to see the region and forms of academic service work on the MPI study website. Academic, administrative activity executors also act as providers of information on service forms, both SIAKAD, tracer studies, academic schedules, and other related documentation.

Formulation of the Problem

The stages of the formulation of the problem (Crouch, 2009) are the stages carried out by researchers together with implementing academic, administrative activities in the MPI study program to formulate the problems they have experienced in academic services. The researcher will also collect the problems experienced (Iqbal et al., 2016) by students and lecturers during the activities.

Develop a Problem Solving Strategy

Problems in academic services in MPI study programs that have been collected are then analyzed one by one, systematically, so that similar problems do not occur in the future. (Rahmat & Mirnawati, 2020) Then there will be a coaching meeting and the formulation of joint activities in the form of training as recommended from the previous findings.

Organizing

Stages of organizing (Van Schie et al., 2011) are carried out by carrying out activities to modify the academic web of MPI study programs and training to fill academic content. This training will be discussed how to make content that is easy access, web maintenance, and service promotion. Researchers and the IT team will also guide this activity.

Launching Change Actions

Stages of change actions (Rahmat & Mirnawati, 2020) are carried out by assisting service admins and MPI study program web journalists, this activity is vital to analyze the behavior of presenters and participants (Iqbal et al., 2016) to see the extent of the success of the training.

Reflection on Activities

Reflection activities carried out (Rahmat & Mirnawati, 2020) by researchers in the form of seminars and web launching of MPI study programs. This activity is expected to be an initial milestone in the change of the administration system in MPI study programs and is expected to be transmitted to other study programs.

Follow up

As a form of follow-up to the activity (Rahmat & Mirnawati, 2020), researchers will still open space for admins and journalists to be given training or ongoing assistance in the educational service process. It is done so that in the future, the management of web-based academic management services (Indrayani, 2011) can be more professional and achieve desired goals.

RESULTS

Web management focuses on three aspects: domain management, visual graphics, and content (content). All three are needed to build a standard website as access to information. Through the web, the MPI Study Program 's academic services can become more professional, structured, and reach needy audiences. As part of this update, web-based academic services in the MPI Study Program are needed to achieve the goal by working with all stakeholders in both study programs and across units (TIPD) within IAIN Palopo 's scope. The website is a bridge for the public to access MPI Study Program information. With the MPI Study Program website, service times can be cut, and information can be more easily accessed and become a means of educational publishing for those studying at the IAIN Palopo MPI Study Program. The implementation of Participatory Action Research took place in the MPI Study Program work unit in IAIN Palopo for 80 working days, starting June 4-September 21, 2018.

Table 1. Schedule of Activities

Design of Activities	June				July				August				September			
	Weeks				Weeks				Weeks				Weeks			
	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
Conducting web development consultations on the Islamic Education Study Program	■															
Registering web sub-domains and collecting content from the Islamic Education Study Program website		■														
Installing web machines on registered subdomains and creating a web framework for Islamic Education Study Program			■													
Designing the form of <i>web</i> display of Islamic Education Management Study Program				■	■											
Make a menu and complete each menu content with types of services, information, and activities related to the Islamic Education Study Program						■	■	■	■	■	■					
Conducting <i>web</i> management training for prospective <i>web</i> admin study programs												■				
Automation of web services published in the Islamic Education Study Program													■	■		

By applying accountability, nationalism, public ethics, quality commitment, and anti-corruption (ANEKA) value to web-based academic management services in the Islamic Education Study Program. Activity stages are:

Conducting consultations related to the design of web design of Islamic Education Management Study Program

Table 2. Consultations to the Design of Web Islamic Education Management Study Program

Activity Stages	The Linkage of Substance	Strengthening Organizational Values
1. Coordinate with the Information Technology and Database Unit (TIPD) related to the preparation of the web design	Public Ethics Establishing coordination between units within an institution	Innovation , creating new things that are better than existing forms of service;
2. Make conclusions from the results of the consultation	Accountability The responsibility must be achieved in the activities	Responsibility , namely to work thoroughly and consistently

Contribution to the Vision and Mission of the Organization:

IAIN Palopo's vision and mission to develop the integration of quality and professional knowledge characterized by local knowledge

Outputs/Results:

Coordinating web design activities for the Islamic Education Study Program

Negative Impact analysis:

If the State Civil Apparatus (ASN) does not update public ethics in conducting MPI Prodi web design consultations, then the potential for fading ways, loss of mutual respect, and difficulty in coordinating activities. Furthermore, if it does not update accountability in the conduct of MPI Prodi web design consultations, it has the potential to make task implementers not responsible

for their tasks and duties, work is carried out following procedures and may create conflicts of interest

Registering Web sub-domains and collecting materials that will be the contents of the Islamic Education Management Study Program website

Table 3. Registering web Sub-Domains and collecting materials website

Activity Stages	The Linkage of Substance	Strengthening Organizational Values
1. Conduct consultations with leaders related to the activities to be carried out	Public Ethics Respect for hierarchy and the importance of establishing coordination between units within an institution	The professionalism that is working in a disciplined, competent and timely manner with the best results;
2. Request for sub-domain web to the Unit of Information Technology and Data Base (TIPD)	Accountability Realize the responsibility obligations that must be achieved in activities	Innovation , namely creating new things that are better than existing forms of service;
3. Preparing design materials and making materials for the web	Quality Commitment Produce high-quality products/services: without flaws, mistakes, and waste.	Responsibilities of working thoroughly and consistently
4. Report the results of the activities		

Contribution to the Vision and Mission of the Organization:

IAIN Palopo's vision and mission to improve the convergence of quality and professional information distinguished by local knowledge

Outputs/Results:

The formation of sub-domains which will become the web address of the Islamic Education Management Study Program

Negative Impact analysis:

If the State Civil Apparatus (ASN) does not amend public ethics and transparency in the registry of the MPI Prodi site subdomain, then the capacity for etiquette to disappear, lack of mutual respect, and difficulty in coordinating activities, it has the potential to make the mission implementer not accountable for carrying out his duties, the function is not done under procedures, and may not lead further

Installing a Web Engine on a Subdomain that has been Registered and Creating a Web Framework of Islamic Education Management Study Program

Table 4. Installing a Web Engine and Creating a Web Framework

Activity Stages	The Linkage of Substance	Strengthening Organizational Values
a. Conduct consultations with leaders related to the activities to be carried out	Quality Commitment Produce high-quality products/services: without defects, errors, and waste.	Professionalism working with the best results disciplined, competent and timely;
b. Installing FTP account (File Transfer Protocol)	Accountability Realize the responsibility obligations that must be achieved in activities	Innovation , Creating new things that are better than existing forms of service;
c. Uploading and installing WordPress 4.9.6 application via FTP account		Responsibilities of working thoroughly and consistently
d. Report the results of the activities		

Figure 4. Install and Upload files via FTP Account on the Domain and Set up WordPress Machine on the domain

Outputs/Results:

Installed WordPress 4.9.6 application to run the Islamic Education Management Study Program website

Negative Impact analysis:

If State Civil Apparatus (ASN) fails to update the quality commitments and accountability for the installation of web machines in the registered subdomain and makes the MPI Prodi web framework, then the potential to decrease the quality of the performance and the results of the work and also the potential to make task implementers not responsible for the performance of their tasks and tasks,

Designing the form of web display of Islamic Education Management Study Program

Table 5. Designing the form of web display

Activity Stages	The Linkage of Substance	Strengthening Organizational Values
1. Conducting consultations with leaders related to web design	<p>Quality Commitment Produce high-quality products/services: without flaws, mistakes, and waste.</p> <p>Accountability Realize the responsibilities for activities</p>	<p>The professionalism that is working in a disciplined, competent and timely manner with the best results;</p> <p>Innovation, Creating new things that are better than existing forms of service;</p> <p>Responsibilities of working thoroughly and consistently</p>
2. Creating a web visual format concept		
3. Consultation of web format to the leadership of the work unit		
4. Improve according to suggestions and results		

Figure 5. Web display design of Islamic Education Management Study Program

Contribution to the Vision and Mission of the Organization:

Web display of the Islamic Education Management Study Program can realize IAIN Palopo's vision and mission to develop quality and professional, scientific integration characterized by local wisdom

Outputs/Results:

Website of the Islamic Education Management Study Program

Negative Impact analysis:

If State Civil Apparatus (ASN) does not update the quality commitments and accountability in the design of the MPI Prodi web-view form, it has the potential to cause a decrease in performance quality and work output, even without consulting with leaders on the design of the MPI Prodi web-view form. Then it has the potential to make the task implementer not be responsible for performing its tasks and functions, the work is performed not according to procedures, and may lead to conflicts of interest.

Make a menu and fill each menu with types of services, information, and activities related to Islamic Education Management Study Program

Table 6. Fill Each Menu With Types of Services, Information, and Activities

Activity Stages	The Linkage of Substance	Strengthening Organizational Values
1. Conducting consultations with leaders	Quality Commitment Produce high-quality products/ services: without defects, without errors, and no waste	The professionalism that is working in a disciplined, competent and timely manner with the best results;
2. Create a web menu concept in the Islamic Education Study Program	Public Ethics	Innovation , Creating new things that are better than existing forms of service;
3. Consultation of the Web menu format of the Islamic Education Management Study Program	Strong values, respect for leadership and importance of cooperation between leaders and subordinates	Responsibilities of working thoroughly and consistently
4. Improve according to suggestions and the results of the consultation	Accountability The platform menu seeks to fulfill the duties of the operations	

Contribution to the Vision and Mission of the Organization:

Create a menu on the Islamic Education Management Study Program web, realize IAIN Palopo's vision and mission to develop the integration of quality and professional knowledge characterized by local knowledge

Figure 6. Menu design on the web of Islamic Education Management Study Program

Outputs/Results:

Installing the menu display needs on the web of Islamic Education Management Study Program

Negative Impact analysis:

If State Civil Apparatus (ASN) does not update quality commitments and public ethics when making menus and filling out the MPI Study Program web, then it has the potential to reduce performance quality and work output, then the potential for fading in manners, loss of mutual respect and difficulty in coordinating activities.

Implementation of web management training to web administrators of Islamic Education Management Study Program

Table 7. Web Management Training to Web Administrators

Activity Stages	The Linkage of Substance	Strengthening Organizational Values
1. Conducting consultations with leaders	Quality Commitment Produce high-quality products/ services: without defects, without errors, and no waste	The professionalism that is working in a disciplined, competent and timely manner with the best results;
2. Guiding managing web study programs to those appointed to manage web study programs	Public Ethics Good ethics, respect for hierarchy, and coordination between leaders and subordinates	Innovation , Creating new things that are better than existing forms of service;
3. Report the results of activities to the head of the work unit	Accountability The web menu seeks to fulfill the responsibilities of the activities	Responsibilities of working thoroughly and consistently

Outputs/Results:

Giving birth to skilled personnel in managing the web of Islamic Education Management Study Program

Contribution to the Vision and Mission of the Organization:

With web management training in the Islamic Education Management Study Program, it can realize IAIN Palopo's vision and mission to develop the integration of quality and professional knowledge characterized by local knowledge

Negative Impact analysis:

If State Civil Apparatus (ASN) fails to update quality commitments and accountability in conducting web management training for prospective MPI web admin programs, it has the potential to reduce the quality of output/training participants.

Making x-banner automation of web services publication Management of Islamic Education Study Program

Table 8. Making x-banner of web services publication

Activity Stages	The Linkage of Substance	Strengthening Organizational Values
1. Consultation with the head of the work unit	Quality Commitment Produce high-quality products/ services: without	The professionalism that is working in a disciplined, competent and timely manner with the best results;

2. Convert service links on the web into QRcode	defects, without errors, and no waste	Innovation , Creating new things that are better than existing forms of service;
3. Designing x-banner automation publication of web services	Public Ethics Strong principles, reverence for leadership and value of cooperation between leaders and subordinates	Responsibilities of working thoroughly and consistently
4. Printing x-banner automation of Prodi web service publications	Accountability Web menu seeks to realize the responsibility	
5. Install x-banner web service publication in front of the office room	obligations that must be achieved in the activities	
6. Report the results of the activities		

Outputs/Results:

X-Banner automation of the publication of web services in Islamic Education Management Study Program

Contribution to the Vision and Mission of the Organization:

With the effort to make the x-banner automation of the publication of web services of Islamic Education Management Study Program, it can realize the vision & mission of IAIN Palopo which seeks to develop quality and professional, scientific integration that is characterized by local wisdom

Negative Impact analysis:

If State Civil Apparatus (ASN) does not improve quality commitment and openness in making MPI Prodi Web Service Publications x-banner automation, it has the potential to reduce the quality of work and may also establish conflicts of interest if the State Civil Apparatus (ASN) does not amend public ethics in reviewing the results of leadership work, the potential for vanishing courtesy,

Constraints in Research

The author's initial constraints relate to facilities, facilities, and infrastructure. Building a web requires the right equipment, such as fast internet access and a computer that can handle graphics. The procedures included in the academic information system include enrollment information, student re-registration, grade processing, financial data processing, course scheduling, and academic reporting. Academic information systems applied in MPI study programs still use many traditional information systems, so there are still many weaknesses, such as academic data that are not well integrated, so redundancy remains. Most academic data is still stored in the form of archives, so the process of finding data is still running slowly, so data processing errors often occur, and reporting processes are still slow.

Anticipation and Solution

To anticipate the obstacles above, the authors optimize both mentors and mentors' discussion and guidance process. The authors also anticipate this by using personal laptop facilities and private internet access at home. The workspace occupied by the author is also shared with the chair of the IAIN Palopo MPI study program. It is a way to facilitate direct coordination of the authors' actualization activities. By intensively coordinating the dean, head of study programs, mentors, and mentors, the work program can be implemented well, and several activities arranged.

DISCUSSION

Indonesia's preconditions realize the country's vision, as stated in Indonesia's 1945 Constitution Preamble. The State Civil Apparatus (ASN) is instrumental in managing the precondition. ASN has made several strategic decisions ranging from policymaking to policy implementation in various development sectors. To this role, a professional ASN figure is needed that can meet his position's competency

standards so that he can perform his official duties effectively and efficiently. Therefore, ASN is required to have ANEKA's fundamental values (Accountability, Nationalism, Public Ethics, Quality Commitment, and Anti - Corruption) as well as ASN's Public Service, Whole Government, and Management as a set of principles that become the foundation of the profession, namely:

Accountability

Accountability applies to the obligations needed (van de Poel, 2011). Accountability refers to each person, organization, or institution's duty to perform the required obligations. Accountability is a duty or liability that must be met, and a report form must exist. A civil servant 's mandate is to ensure the realization of public values, including (1) the ability to make good choices when conflicts of interest arise between public interests and the interests of sectors, groups and individuals; (2) understanding and awareness to avoid and prevent the involvement of civil servants in practical politics; (3) treating citizens equally and fairly in government.

Nationalism

Nationalism is vital for every ASN. Nationalism is the foundation for the State Civil Apparatus (Berman, 1998) to realize its functions and duties with a focus on public, nation, and state interests. Otherwise, often interpreted as nationalism. ASN, which has strong nationalism, is ASN, which: 1) understands and understands Pancasila 's values in fulfilling its duties. 2) Carry out its duties and functions as public policymakers and implementers in updating the nationalist spirit and stable national outlook. 3) Work professionally as a high-integrity public servant. 4) Become a state extension in realizing the nation's unity and integrity.

Public Ethics

Public ethics reflects standards/norms that determine good/bad, right/wrong decisions, behavior to direct public policies to fulfill public service responsibilities. (Hejka-Ekins, 1988) The fundamental values of public ethics include: 1) upholding values in the ideology of the State of Pancasila, 2) being loyal and maintaining the Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia of 1945, 3) performing professional and impartial tasks and taking responsibility for implementing government policies and programs, 4) making decisions based on the principle of expertise.

Quality Commitment

Quality commitment is implementing results-oriented public services. (van de Poel, 2011) Quality commitment values include: prioritizing commitment to satisfaction and services that touch the heart, maintain, and maintain. The fundamental values of quality orientation in providing excellent service include: 1) Prioritizing public satisfaction commitment, and providing services that touch the heart, maintaining and maintaining the public's loyalty. 2) Produce high-quality products/services: without defects, without errors, and without waste and adapting to changes that occur, both in terms of shifting demands on public needs and technological development; 3) use scientific and innovative approaches to the problem - solving and decision-making; and work towards continuous improvement in various ways, including education, training, developers.

Anti-Corruption

Anti-corruption is an action or movement taken to eradicate all behaviors or actions against norms for personal gain (Setiyono & McLeod, 2010), directly or indirectly harming the state or society. Anti-corruption fundamental values include: honest, caring, independent, disciplined, accountable, hard-working, simple, courageous and fair

Public Services

According to Law No. 25 of 2009, the definition of public services is an activity or series of activities to meet service needs under statutory regulations for each citizen and resident of goods (Council et al., 2012), services, and administrative services provided by public service providers. Three critical elements in public services: first, the organization of public service providers; second, the recipient of the service (customers), namely the persons or organizations concerned; and third, the

authority given and received by the recipient. Participatory, transparent, responsive, non - discriminatory, easy and cheap, effective and efficient, accessible, accountable and fair

The Whole of Government (WOG)

The whole of government (WOG) is a governance approach (Christensen & Lægreid, 2006) that unites collaborative government efforts from the entire sector in a broader scope of coordination to achieve policy development, program management, and public service goals. WoG explains how government agencies work across borders or sectors to achieve common goals and as an integrated government response to specific issues. WoG shows or explains how government agencies work across borders or sectors to achieve common goals and as an integrated government response to specific issues. (Sugiastuti, 2020) WoG becomes important, growing as a government-conscious approach. First, there are external factors such as public encouragement to integrate policies, development programs, and services to create better governance. Developing more sophisticated information technology, situations, and policy dynamics also drives WoG 's importance in uniting government institutions as public policy and service providers. (Bamber et al., 2014) Second, related to internal factors with a sectoral capacity imbalance phenomenon resulting from nuances of competition between development sectors. Third, particularly in the Indonesian context, the diversity of backgrounds, values, cultures, customs, and other backgrounds supports the potential for national disintegration. As a formal institution, the government is obliged to encourage the growth of national adhesive values to ensure the unity of these national elements in one NKRI frame. The core values of the Whole Government are legal certainty, public interest, proportionality, professionalism, transparency, and efficiency.

ASN Management

ASN management is an activity that puts more emphasis on regulating professional employee arrangements, so it becomes an excellent resource for civil service and always follows changing times. (Plowden, 1985) ASN employees are state apparatus implementing policies determined by government agency leadership and free from the influence and intervention of all groups and political parties. ASN employees are prohibited from becoming party members and administrators. In addition to distancing bureaucracy from the influence of political parties, this is intended to ensure the ASN 's integrity, cohesiveness, and unity, and can focus all attention, thoughts, and energy on its assigned tasks. ASN works and plays a role in providing professional, high - quality public services. Public service is an activity to fulfill service needs according to laws and regulations for every citizen and resident of goods, services, and administrative services organized by public service providers with the goal of customer satisfaction. Therefore, ASN must be professional in providing community services. ASN has the function, duty, and role in enhancing the unity and integrity of Indonesia's Unitary State. ASN always and fully obeys Pancasila, the Constitution of 1945, the State, and the Government. ASN always upholds ASN 's dignity and always prioritizes state interests over individuals and groups (Setiyono & McLeod, 2010). ASN Law states that one of them is the principle of unity and integrity in ASN's implementation and management policy. ASN must always prioritize and prioritize national unity and integrity (primarily national and state interests). ASN's core values include: professional, professional ethics, neutrality, corruption-free, collusion, and nepotism

CONCLUSION

Preparing this participatory action work was a framework for upgrading ANEKA principles (accountability, nationalism, civic ethics, efficiency commitment, and anti-corruption) in introducing the important training exercises in the civil service. The application of the material substance obtained during the basic training will form a strong ASN character, namely ASN, which can behave and act professionally in serving the community in order to create a highly dedicated ASN in the future and be a driver of national progress. Various parties, including leaders and employees in the Palopo IAIN community, sponsored this operation. Activities carried out for 80 days to resolve the issue of the web-based academic services in the Islamic Education Management Study Program IAIN Palopo, namely 1) conducting consultations on web design of the Islamic Education Management Study Program; 2) Registering the web sub - domain and collecting the content of the Islamic Education Management Study Program web; 3) installing web machines in registered sub-domains and creating a web framework for

the Islamic Education Management Study Program; 4) Develop a form of web display of the Islamic Education Management Study Program; 5) create menus and fill each menu with types of services, information, and activities related to the Islamic Education Management Study Program; 6) implement web management training for prospective web administrators of the Islamic Education Management Study Program; 7) Making x-banner web services in the Islamic Education Management Study Program.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors present thanks to IAIN Palopo's, especially the chancellor and chair of the Islamic Education Management Study Program. They have facilitated this research, and hopefully, this research can contribute to the study of management education in Islamic tertiary institutions.

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